

Onboard Radar Processing Framework for Maritime Surveillance with a High-Altitude Platform

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Abstract—This paper presents an overview of an onboard maritime surveillance radar processing framework for stratospheric high-altitude platforms (HAP). It is suited for DLR’s compact multichannel HAPSAR radar sensor envisioned as a payload for the DLR HAP. It enables ship detection and tracking with long observation times, high-resolution image sequence generation, and estimation of ship dimensions and moving direction. Furthermore, by leveraging parallel processing, the framework achieves onboard processing with reduced computational load, enhancing processing efficiency. Experimental radar data from DLR’s DBFSAR airborne radar system and the TerraSAR-X satellite validate the framework as a proof of concept.

Index Terms—maritime security, ships, radar, HAP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Given the escalating maritime threats worldwide, a robust security system capable of surveilling suspected ships for threat detection and response is of paramount national importance. Such a system not only protects national borders but also monitors critical marine infrastructure, such as wind parks, over-water region in the neighborhood of underwater pipelines and communication cables, from potential threats posed by these ships.

For this purpose, surveillance systems such as the automatic identification system (AIS), coastal radars, and marine radars are widely deployed [1]. However, these systems have inherent limitations. For example, smaller ships often lack AIS transponders, and some ships may deliberately deactivate them to evade detection. Marine radars have a limited range, while coastal radars, despite offering extended coverage due to their elevated installations, are primarily effective in coastal regions. As a result, they are less suitable for detecting ships in open waters.

To address these surveillance gaps, air- and spaceborne radar sensors can work alongside existing systems and offer all-weather, day-and-night data acquisition capabilities with high resolution [2]. While spaceborne radars offer wide-area coverage, airborne radars enable shorter revisits and longer observation times [3]. However, conventional aircraft are constrained by high operational costs and limited flight endurance, making them impractical for regions requiring continuous monitoring.

Future high-altitude platforms (HAPs), also referred to as high-altitude pseudo-satellites (HAPS), operating in the

stratosphere at altitudes of 15–25 km, offer extended endurance far beyond that of conventional aircraft. These solar-powered platforms can remain operational for several weeks [4], facilitating quasi-continuous and wide-area monitoring of exclusive economic zones and critical offshore infrastructure. Ships entering the surveillance region can be detected and tracked with long observation times.

In this paper, an onboard maritime surveillance processing framework suited for multichannel radar sensors is presented. It is envisaged for operational use with the compact HAPSAR sensor [5] on the DLR HAP [6]. Fig. 1 illustrates an overview of the maritime surveillance system to be implemented. Since the DLR HAP is still under development and the first low-altitude flight of HAPSAR is planned for the second half of 2025, the framework’s effectiveness is demonstrated using radar data acquired with DLR’s DBFSAR airborne radar system [7] and the German TerraSAR-X radar satellite.

II. ONBOARD SURVEILLANCE PROCESSING FRAMEWORK WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The onboard surveillance processor, consisting of several modules, is shown in the bottom right of Fig. 1. In the figure the modules are organized into five separate processes running in parallel, either as separate processes or threads. Python’s multiprocessing library [8] is primarily utilized for the implementation.

The framework is built around a PostgreSQL database [9] structure as core, where all relevant information about the detected ships is stored. PostgreSQL, being an object-relational database management system, supports simultaneous read and write operations. The entire framework runs on the HAPSAR onboard computer.

In the following, each process within the framework including experimental results achieved with DBFSAR and TerraSAR-X data is briefly discussed.

In **Process 1** ships are detected and tracked and their geographical positions, line-of-sight velocities and moving directions are estimated and stored in the database. Additionally, false targets or finished target tracks are terminated through a powerful track management system [10]. **Process 1** is the key process as it carries out the crucial first step of detection. Experimental detection and tracking results of small

Fig. 1. Maritime surveillance with a high-altitude platform. Left: multichannel data acquisition geometry; top right: onboard computer; bottom right: processing framework.

Fig. 2. Detection and tracking results over Ammersee in southern Germany using the multichannel DBFSAR radar sensor. Top left: test site; bottom left: detection and tracking of small boats (orange dots) in the given region of interest (ROI). In the figure known targets with their GPS tracks (white dots), along with some false and unknown target tracks can be seen. Middle: zoomed-in detail of two selected boats; right: boats used in the experiment.

id_raw [PK] bigint	insertdate timestamp without time zone	raw_message text
1	2024-10-02 10:23:38	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,152IS=kP?w<SF0I4Q@>4?w...
2	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,152IS=?P?w3VMPh>ton>4?...
3	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,C1mg=5@0I;78mP=18D02P1...
4	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,H>eq'dA@TqT<5@0000000...
5	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,H>eq'dDN3?=1B00=1ECC00...
6	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,B1mg=5@0N3?8mP=18D0N...
7	2024-10-02 10:23:40	!AIVDM,1,1,,B,152IS>0P?w9p@@PDAnP>4...

Fig. 3. A screenshot of some raw AIS messages along with their corresponding timestamps in the database table.

moving boats along with their corresponding GPS tracks using DBFSAR data as input is shown in Fig. 2.

Process 2 decodes ship AIS [11] messages received by a dual-channel onboard AIS receiver. The received messages, along with their timestamps, are stored in a dedicated database table. A screenshot of some raw AIS messages in the database table is shown in Fig. 3.

Process 3 generates high-resolution ISAR (inverse synthetic aperture radar) image sequences of ships [13]. Ship data patches obtained from the target tracks in **Process 1** are used as input to create fully focused ISAR images. ISAR imaging, in general, is a computationally intensive process as it requires Fast Fourier Transforms (FFTs), inverse FFTs (IFFTs), and sophisticated adaptive motion compensation algorithms. Without multiprocessing, the detection and tracking of other targets would only begin after completing the ISAR imaging of the first target, leading to increased and unaccepted long processing time, preventing any operational use of the framework.

High-resolution ISAR images and fully focused SAR images can be used for estimating ship dimensions and heading angle accurately, refining its motion parameters retrieved from **Process 1**, and aid later on in ship classification for recognition and identification purposes. Fig. 4 shows an exemplary ship size and heading angle estimation results obtained with TerraSAR-X data.

Process 4 fuses ship positions obtained from the AIS data with radar-based geocoded detections. An example is shown in Fig. 5. The geocoded radar detections of the ships HAM 316 and LANGELAND are merged along with their corresponding AIS positions, with a radar position accuracy better than 30 m [14]. Detections that do not match any available AIS data but were tracked in the data could indicate potential suspicious targets, requiring further investigation and appropriate action.

Finally, in **Process 5**, targets that have been tracked for a certain amount of time are extracted and visualized, typically as KML files on Google Earth, as shown in Fig. 5. However, the provision of the data in other standardized or non-standardized format is also possible by adding, for instance, a conversion module in **Process 5**.

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper a maritime surveillance processing framework for the HAPSAR multichannel compact radar sensor, designed

for deployment onboard DLR's high-altitude platform (HAP) is presented. The effectiveness of the proposed processing chain has been demonstrated using real radar data from DLR's multichannel airborne DBFSAR system and spaceborne TerraSAR-X satellite.

The framework operates in a multiprocessing environment, leveraging Python's multiprocessing capabilities and a PostgreSQL database. The framework has been successfully implemented on the HAPSAR onboard computer and tested offline with real radar data, and has been found sufficiently fast for envisaged maritime surveillance. The processing modules, as illustrated in Fig. 1, are fully operational and have been extensively tested on various air- and spaceborne radar datasets, covering different test sites, ship sizes and their moving directions. Looking ahead, the first low-altitude test flight with HAPSAR will take place at the end of 2025 on an ultra light aircraft, which will provide us additional data in the future.

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Fig. 4. Ship size and heading estimation results using three different exemplary ship image patches acquired with the TerraSAR-X SAR satellite [12].

Fig. 5. Geocoded radar detections (orange dots) of two ships around Cuxhaven with their corresponding AIS positions (white dots). Their detailed view is shown on the right [10].

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